

Kinetics and Mechanism of Chlorination of Phenol by *N*-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one in Acid Medium[†]

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Kinetic study of chlorination of phenol in 75% (v/v) aqueous ethanol by *N*-chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (NCP) in acid medium, exhibits first order dependence both on [substrate] and [oxidant]. The rate increases with increase in [H⁺], ionic strength and dielectric constant. The kinetic parameters have been calculated.

The kinetic measurements have also been made with some *meta*- and *para*- substituted phenols. Here the order in NCP is unity and that in substrate varies depending on the nature of the substituent present in the ring. A suitable mechanism has been formulated. Isokinetic and Exner plots give straight lines with fine correlation coefficients.

CHLORINATION of reactive aromatic substrates has been studied with a wide variety of chlorinating agents like chlorine, *N*-chloro compounds^{1,2} and peroxydisulphate and chloride ions³. Recently the use of NCP as oxidising agent⁴⁻⁷ has been reported. The present study shows that NCP can also behave as a chlorinating agent. In all those cases the reacting species appears to be the protonated *N*-chloropiperidone. Here we propose that the chlorine of the protonated piperidone first attacks the oxygen atom of phenol to form a complex which then gets rearranged to *o*-chlorophenol.

Experimental

N-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one was prepared and purified as described earlier⁴. Phenol (AnalaR) was purified by distillation before use. Ethanol was freed from carbonyl compounds by refluxing it successively with silver nitrate and potassium hydroxide, and then distilled through Dufton column. Double-distilled water was used throughout. All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

The kinetic studies were carried out in 75% (v/v) ethanol-water in pseudo-first order conditions. The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted NCP by the standard iodometric method and NCP was used as a primary standard. The kinetics were followed generally up to 75% completion of the reaction and rate coefficients (*k'*) were determined from log (titre) vs time plots by the least-square method. In case of some of the substituted phenols, *k'* values were calculated from the initial rate because of the retardation noticed after 30% completion⁸.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing an excess of NCP to react with the substrate and the unreacted NCP was estimated after the completion of the reaction. The stoichiometry of the reaction was 1 : 1.

The product *o*-chlorophenol was characterised by preparing aryloxyacetic acid derivative, m.p. 141° (lit. 141°).

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of chlorination of phenol by NCP was investigated at several initial concentration of the reactants (Table 1) and the reaction proceeded

TABLE 1 - EFFECT OF VARYING [OXIDANT], [SUBSTRATE] AND [H⁺] ON RATE OF CHLORINATION OF PHENOL WITH NCP

Solvent: 75% ethanol - water (v/v), Temp. = 30°,
 $\mu = 1.25 \times 10^{-1}$ mol dm⁻³.

[NCP] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Substrate] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 mol dm ⁻³	<i>k'</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.5	2.5	1.25	0.41
1.0	2.5	1.25	0.40
1.5	2.5	1.25	0.41
2.0	2.5	1.25	0.42
2.5	2.5	1.25	0.40
1.0	2.0	4.00	2.26
1.0	2.5	4.00	2.66
1.0	3.0	4.00	3.39
1.0	3.5	4.00	3.93
1.0	4.0	4.00	4.34
1.0	4.5	4.00	5.24
1.0 ^a	2.5	1.00	0.85
1.0 ^a	2.5	2.00	1.77
1.0 ^a	2.5	3.00	2.58
1.0 ^a	2.5	4.00	3.45

^a $\mu = 5.0 \times 10^{-1}$ mol dm⁻³.

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smoothly at 30° in aqueous ethanol medium. At low concentrations of NCP and when phenol was in large excess, the reaction was found to be first order in NCP as shown by linear plots of log (a-x) against time with a correlation coefficient >0.99.

A variation in the substrate concentration showed a first order dependence. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k') calculated at different [H⁺] were found to increase linearly (Table 1) and the plot of log k' vs log [H⁺] gave a straight line with unit slope.

Increase in ionic strength as well as the dielectric constant of the medium increased the rate of the reaction (Table 2). Though the percentage of alcohol was changed, there was no appreciable change in the pH of the medium. Hence the variations in k' values may be attributed to the change in dielectric constant and not due to the variation in [H⁺]. The rate constants were measured in the temperature range of 30-40° and the activation parameters calculated (Table 3).

TABLE 2 - EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT ON REACTION RATE

[Phenol]₀ = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NCP]₀ = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30°, [H⁺] = 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³

[NaClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	Alcohol %	k' × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.00 ^b	75	0.82
0.05 ^b	75	0.97
0.10 ^b	75	1.18
0.20 ^b	75	1.33
0.25 ^b	75	1.57
0.0	40	20.23
0.0	50	11.10
0.0	60	5.64
0.0	80	2.61

^b[H⁺] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

TABLE 3 - FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS, ORDER IN SUBSTRATE, ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION FOR SUBSTITUTED-PHENOLS

[NCP] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Substrate] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Solvent: 75% ethanol-water (v/v)

Substituent	k' × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹ *	Order	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
None	2.66	1.0	73.10	-71.46
p-CH ₃	5.21	1.0	49.75	-144.02
m-CH ₃	25.01	1.0	39.63	-164.24
p-Cl	0.34	0.87	76.54	-77.83
m-Cl	1.93	1.0	44.48	-169.64
p-Br	0.37	0.33	65.63	-144.00
m-Br	3.05	0.60	56.13	-127.06
p-NO ₂	0.26	0	70.29	-101.00
m-NO ₂	0.36	0	55.75	-140.31
p-OCH ₃	1.20	0	64.45	-106.24

*At 30°.

When the above kinetic study was carried out with some of the substituted-phenols the reaction showed first order dependence in [NCP] but the

order in the [substrate] varied depending on the nature of the substituent present in the ring. The variation in rate constants for p-Cl, p-Br and m-Br-phenols are given in Table 4. The double-reciprocal plots of k' against [substrate] gave straight lines with finite intercepts for the above three phenols, (r > 0.98) indicating very clearly the formation of Michaelis-Menton type of complex between the reactants. The rate constants (at 30°) order, ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] values for the phenols are given in Table 4

TABLE 4 - EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] ON REACTION RATE FOR SUBSTITUTED-PHENOLS

[NCP] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Solvent: 75% ethanol-water (v/v), [H⁺] = 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30°

[Substrate] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k' × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	
2.50	3.36
3.75	4.20
4.30	4.82
5.00	6.54
<i>p</i> -Bromophenol	
2.50	3.72
3.75	4.31
5.00	4.68
<i>m</i> -Bromophenol	
1.48	4.15
1.85	5.15
2.50	6.05
3.33	6.85

If NCPH⁺ were the oxidising species one should expect an increase in rate as [HClO₄] increases; this is indeed what is observed in the present investigation. Previous studies established this kind of equilibrium between NCP and NCPH⁺ 4,5. Considering the above fact and other experimental findings the following mechanism has been proposed.

When the complex is stable, the rate law can be derived as

$$[\text{>N}^+\text{HCl}] = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} [\text{>N}-\text{Cl}] [\text{H}^+]$$

Applying the steady state approximation for the complex formed in step (2), the rate law becomes,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{>NCl}] = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{>NCl}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Phenol}]}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + [\text{Phenol}]}$$

This rate law explains the fractional order dependence on [substrate]. The variation in the order dependence in respect of the different substituted-phenols is explained by invoking different rate controlling steps in the above mechanism, i.e. if $k_2 \gg k_1, k_{-1}, k_{-2}$, a zero order dependence; if $k_2 \ll k_1, k_{-2}, k_3$, a first order; and if $k_2 \approx k_1$ and when the complex is stable, a fractional order dependence would be obtained.

In the case of unsubstituted phenol since the complex is unstable, the rate law becomes,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{>NCl}] = \frac{k_2 k_3 k_1}{k_{-2} k_{-1}} [\text{>NCl}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Phenol}] \quad (5)$$

Exner⁹ and Isokinetic plots gave straight lines with a fine correlation coefficients ($r > 0.96$) indicating that the above phenols are undergoing chlorination by a common mechanism.

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